

1 Lefty2 functions in embryonic stem cell fate choice during endoderm lineage specification.

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for Lefty2 in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo*
11 *sapiens*.

12 Citations

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1. Meno, C., Shimono, A., Saijoh, Y., Yashiro, K., Mochida, K., Ohishi, S., Noji, S., Kondoh, H. and Hamada, H., 1998. lefty-1 is required for left-right determination as a regulator of lefty-2 and nodal. *Cell*, 94(3), pp.287-297.